

Graphene-high rich polycaprolactone nanofibers prepared via alternating current electrospinning as advanced sustainable sorbents for environmental analysis

Pavel Holec^a, Martina Háková^b, Ivona Kolichová^b, Jan Vinter^a, Tomáš Kalous^a, Markéta Hujerová^a, Dalibor Šatínský^{b,*}, Jakub Erben^{a,*}

^a The Technical University of Liberec, Faculty of Textile Engineering, Department of Nonwovens and Nanofibrous Materials, Studentská 1402/2, Liberec 46001, Czech Republic

^b Charles University, Faculty of Pharmacy in Hradec Králové, Department of Analytical Chemistry, Ak. Heyrovského 1203, Hradec Králové 50003, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

The increasing demand for environmental quality control demands advanced analytical tools for potentially harmful substances monitoring. The monitoring tools for trace level contaminant analyses typically rely on advanced chromatographic methods coupled with sensitive detectors and sustainable sample pre-treatment techniques to remove ballast matrix components. This study presents a straightforward approach for preparing a novel nanofibrous composite extraction sorbent based on biodegradable poly-ε-caprolactone (PCL) polymer nanofibers and graphene (GR) nanoparticles prepared via alternating current (AC) electrospinning of polymer solution. Using AC electrospinning, it was possible to prepare more voluminous and porous layers with a higher GR particle content compared to the more common direct current (DC) method. The new composite material demonstrates high extraction efficiency of target analytes for chemical analysis of surface water pollutants while offering. The PCL-GR composite, with GR particle content up to 45 wt%, was self-supporting, flexible, and did not require energy-intensive carbonization processes as more common GR materials. The composite was successfully tested for the retention of selected pesticides, insecticides, and residues typical for industrial pollution using on-line extraction coupled to chromatography, demonstrating its potential as solid-phase extraction (SPE) material for a common surface water pollutants.

1. Introduction

Discovering new methods and approaches for simplifying sample analysis is one of the key directions in which both analytical and environmental chemistry is heading. Solid-phase extraction (SPE) is a widely used technique for sample pretreatment, an essential step in chemical analysis. It serves to remove contaminants from the analyzed sample while concentrating the analytes. Considering the sources of chromatographic errors, more than one-third originate from sample preparation. Furthermore, this stage accounts for approximately two-thirds of the total time required for the analytical process, making sample pretreatment one of the most critical

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: satinsky@faf.cuni.cz (D. Šatínský), jakub.erben@tul.cz (J. Erben).

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steps in the entire analysis workflow. This is particularly true for environmental samples, which often have complex matrices that require specific preparation (Backe and Field., 2012). Automation of process is one way to improve the analytical methods. On-line coupling the SPE step and HPLC belongs to the advanced trends in this field. It provides reproducible experimental conditions, with minimal demands for the operator's skills and effect of external conditions (Háková et al., 2020, 2018a).

Among the commercially used sorbents for SPE, porous synthetic polymers are common representatives (Torabi et al., 2024; Fontanals et al., 2019). Their main advantage lies in the great diversity of chemical and physicochemical properties of usable polymers, which can further be modified to achieve a wide range of possible interactions between the sorbent and the analyte (Fontanals et al., 2020). The most used polymers for SPE sorbents include polystyrene (PS) and its copolymer with divinylbenzene (DVB). Due to their high hydrophobicity and low wettability, such materials are not suitable for the retention of more polar analytes from water compartment and can be chemically modified with more polar groups or comonomers (Huang et al., 2020; Ning et al., 2022; Yin et al., 2019). Polymer particles are most commonly used, or networks formed by their additional crosslinking.

A promising innovative alternative to sorbent particles could be polymeric nanofibers (An et al., 2021; Qi et al., 2008; Ifegwu et al., 2014), whose specific surface area is comparable to that of commonly used polymeric sorbent particles (Fontanals et al., 2020). These materials are also compact and mechanically self-supporting, simplifying their processing into extraction sorbents. Similar to particle-based sorbents, fiber-based counterparts can also be further functionalized by additional materials (nanoparticles, nanotubes, metal organic frameworks, crown-ethers, and surface coatings) can be incorporated during or after their fabrication, or the fiber surface can be chemically modified to further alter their final properties and expand the portfolio of their usability for sorption purposes (Chigome et al., 2011).

Although nanofibers can be prepared using various methods (Alghoraibi and Alomari, 2018), electrospinning of polymer solutions is one of the most commonly used methods for their production. Its advantages include the variability of the spinning process, and thus the resulting fiber structures, the ability to spin a wide range of polymers, the possibility of incorporating soluble and insoluble substances into the resulting fibers, as well as relatively low costs for equipment and the production process (Xue et al., 2019). By far the most frequently used technology is direct current (DC) electrospinning, which typically results in formation of only thin planar sheets with a limited degree of overall porosity. These factors greatly limit the possibilities of its use as an on-line high-pressure SPE method. When compared to DC electrospinning, a less common method is alternating current (AC) electrospinning, which offers advantages for sorbent preparation, such as the preparation of fibrous materials with higher porosity and voluminousness (Pokorný et al., 2014). At the same time, it enables to incorporate higher number of additives into the electrospun solution than the standard DC method. When comparing the application potential of DC and AC nanofibrous layers for extraction purpose, AC materials provide superior performance due to their higher porosity and mechanical durability, leading to improved extraction efficiency and repeatability of analyses (Erben et al., 2022).

Poly- ϵ -caprolactone (PCL) is one of the widely used polymers for electrospinning fabrication of nanofibers (Cipitria et al., 2011). PCL is a semicrystalline linear aliphatic polyester with a low glass transition temperature (-60 °C) and melting temperature (50–70 °C) (Ainhua et al., 2023). This polymer is biodegradable, but its degradation is not so rapid as to compromise its functionality in extraction applications, making biodegradability an additional advantage of this material. PCL is widely used in medicine and bioengineering (Mochane et al., 2019), as well as a sorbent material for SPE (Topsyoy et al., 2022; Tahmasebi, 2018).

The possibility of incorporating modifying substances into fibers during electrospinning can be utilized for the preparation of composite materials combining a carrier polymer and functional particles, such as graphene particles (Torabi et al., 2024). Graphene, as a planar, nonpolar, and rigid moiety could affect the extraction properties of the resulting material, via hydrophobic effect and π - π interactions (Cipitria et al., 2011). Due to its electron-rich, double-sided polyaromatic structure, graphene exhibits strong affinity for aromatic compounds, which is particularly advantageous for interacting with common water pollutants that are typically aromatic in nature (Háková et al., 2018a). However, using graphene in on-line extraction flow techniques could be very problematic, due to very small particle size. This problem could be overcome by using nanofibers as a scaffold where the graphene is incorporated. Then, extraction properties of graphene-based composite results from properties of both parts – polymer and graphene. In the available literature, two basic approaches to prepare nanofiber-graphene composites are commonly described. The first involves electrospinning a polymer solution with the addition of graphene, where the resulting nanofibers typically contain only a few percent of graphene (Matsumoto et al., 2013; Bao et al., 2010; Abolhasani et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2013; Song et al., 2015). For materials requiring higher graphene concentrations, a method involving the carbonization of a carbon-based material (e.g., nanofibers) is used, producing a material that can contain over 90 % graphene (Kuzmenko et al., 2017; Song et al., 2014). However, this method results in the loss of mechanical properties of the product, rendering it brittle. This drawback is addressed by incorporating a fibrous or planar carrier, which, however, reduces the relative graphene content in the material.

We focused on the preparation of high-content graphene-polycaprolactone composite nanofibers via AC electrospinning of polymer solution without the use of a carbonization step and their application as extraction sorbent for on-line extraction high performance liquid chromatography (SPE-HPLC) application in environmental analysis. Different ration of the graphene content in polymer solution was tested during fabrication process and the effect on the extraction yield of contaminants was evaluated. Model contaminants were selected from the group of aromatic compounds with various substituents (bisphenols, chlorphenols, insecticides) due to the expected influence of the graphene content on enhanced extraction yield. Graphene-free polycaprolactone was also used to compare the effect of native polymer on extraction, which in previous studies represented a very interesting alternative to commercial C18 or polymeric MIP/RAM sorbents (Martina et al., 2018; Kholová et al., 2023b, 2023a). Thus, we showed a new method for fabrication of carbon-rich sorbent that exhibits good affinity for aromatic pollutants, attributed to the presence of high content of graphene.

2. Experimental part

2.1. Materials

Poly- ϵ -caprolactone pellets (M_w 80,000 g/mol, CAS: 83259-71-6) were purchased from Polysciences, Inc. (Warrington, Pennsylvania, USA). Formic acid (p.a., CAS: 64-18-6), acetic acid (p.a., CAS: 64-19-7), and acetone (p.a., CAS: 67-64-1) were obtained from Penta (Prague, Czech Republic). Graphene nanoplatelets (surface area 750 m²/g, CAS: 7782-42-5) with particle size below 2 μ m were, bisphenol A (≥ 99 %, CAS: 80-05-7), bisphenol C (≥ 99 %, 79-97-0), bisphenol S (≥ 98 %, CAS: 80-09-1), bisphenol Z (≥ 99 %, CAS: 843-55-0), bisphenol AF (≥ 99 %, CAS: 1478-61-1), bisphenol AP (≥ 99 %, CAS: 1571-75-1), 3-chlorophenol (98.0 %, CAS: 108-43-0), fenoxycarb (99.5 %, CAS: 72490-01-8), hydroxypyren (98.0 %, CAS: 5315-79-7), deltamethrin (99.6 %, CAS: 52918-63-5) and kadethrin (90.8 %, CAS: 58769-20-3), acetonitrile (HPLC grade, CAS: 75-05-08) and methanol (HPLC grade, CAS: 67-56-1) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany). Ultra-pure water was prepared by a Milli-Q system (Millipore, St. Luis, Missouri, USA).

2.2. Spinning solution

2.2.1. Preparation

The PCL solution was prepared by dissolving PCL granules in a mixture of formic acid and acetic acid (w/w 1:1) to achieve a final concentration of 14.3 %. The dissolution process took 12 h at room temperature using a magnetic stirrer. Once the PCL was completely dissolved, the resulting solution was diluted with acetone under constant stirring to obtain a polymer concentration of 10 %. This resulted in a final solvent ratio of 1:1:1. Graphene was added to the stirring solutions in mass ratios relative to the polymer (PCL:GR) of 10:0, 10:1, 10:2, 10:3, 10:4, 10:5, 10:6, 10:7, 10:8, 10:9, and 10:10. This theoretical composition was also used to label the individual fiber material samples. Prior to electrospinning, the solutions were sonicated using a probe sonicator three times for 10 s each to avoid excessive heating of the solution and sedimentation of graphene particles.

2.2.2. Characterization

Viscosity, specific electrical conductivity, and surface tension were determined for each of the prepared PCL solutions. Viscosity measurements were performed using a Haake Rotovisco (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Prague, Czech Republic) with a cone-plate geometry in a continuous mode. The cone used was C35/1°Ti L, with a gap size of 0.2 mm, and the measurement was conducted over 30 s with a linear increase in shear rate from 100 to 3000 s⁻¹. Each measurement was repeated at least three times.

Specific electrical conductivity was measured using an Eutech Instruments CON 510 conductometer (Eutech Instruments, Landsmeer, The Netherlands) with an acid-resistant probe K10/6MM8. Each sample was measured five times.

Surface tension of the solutions was determined using the maximum bubble pressure method, utilizing a PocketDyne device (Krüss, Hamburg, Germany), with a bubble lifetime of approximately 210 ms. Each solution was measured twelve times. All measurements were carried out at a temperature of 22 °C.

Fig. 1. Electrospinning setup (a) with a rotating drum collector (1), collected fibrous material (2), nanofibrous plume (3), overflow electrode (4), and magnetic clutch (5). Cross-sectional detail of the electrode (b) with an overflow disk electrode (6), screw pump (7), power supply (8), and reservoir with circulating polymer solution (9).

2.3. Electrospinning set-up

The prepared 10 % PCL solution and the PCL+GR solutions were electrospun using an overflow electrode with a screw pump via the AC electrospinning method (Fig. 1). The polymer solution was placed in a reservoir, from which it was pumped to the top of the charged electrode using a screw pump. The advantage of using a screw pump with closed solution circulation was the continuous mixing, which prevented the agglomeration of graphene particles. The alternating current applied on the electrode was of frequency 50 Hz with a sinusoidal waveform, and the effective voltage 40 kV. Fibers were formed from the tip of the electrode, with the resulting fiber bundle being carried by the electric wind onto a grounded rotating drum collector covered with antistatic spunbond-type nonwoven polypropylene fabric (surface weight 18 g/m²). The distance between the collector and the electrode was 250 mm, and the collector's peripheral velocity was 30 m/s. Electrospinning was conducted at room temperature with a relative humidity of 45 %.

2.4. Nanofibrous material characterization

2.4.1. Surface morphology

The surface morphology of the prepared nanofibrous material samples was analyzed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) Tescan Vega3 (Tescan, Brno, Czech Republic) at an acceleration voltage of 10 kV. Prior to imaging, the samples were coated with a 7 nm layer of gold using a rotary vacuum sputter coater Q150R (Quorum, Lewes, UK). Manual measurements of fiber diameters from the obtained images were conducted using the ImageJ software (version 1.54 g, Bethesda, Maryland, USA), with 300 fiber diameters measured for each sample.

2.4.2. Total porosity

A gravimetric method was used to determine the total porosity of the fibrous material. For each sample, a layer of material with a total area of 100 cm² was taken, and its thickness was measured using a digital micrometer 49–63 (Testing Machines, Delaware, USA) at a pressure of 400 Pa according to the standard test procedure EDANA – NWSP 120.1.R0. The weight was measured on analytical scales KERN ADJ 200–4 (KERN, Balingen, Germany) with an accuracy of four decimal places. The specific densities of PCL (1.145 g/cm³ (Rosa et al., 2004)) and GR (2.2 g/cm³ (Hwang et al., 2013)) were used for calculating the total porosity.

2.4.3. Water contact angle

The contact angle was measured using a See System goniometer (Advex Instruments, Brno, Czech Republic). A 5 µl water droplet was applied to each nanofiber sample. Each droplet was then photographed using the See System software (version 6.2, Brno, Czech Republic). The evaluation was conducted using the three-point method, where three points were marked on the picture (both ends where the droplet touched the nanofiber layer, and the highest point of the droplet). The contact angle was then automatically calculated by the software.

2.4.4. Specific surface area

The specific surface area was determined using the gas adsorption isotherm method based on the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) equation, employing an Autosorb iQ device (Anton Paar, Graz, Austria) in standard mode. Fiber samples (1000 mg) were placed in glass cells and degassed for 24 h at 50 °C before measurement. Krypton was used for the analysis, and the data were processed using ASiQwin software (version 4.0).

2.4.5. Graphene content determination

A thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was used to determine the amount of GR in the PCL fibers. This exploited the possibility of complete thermal and Thermo oxidative degradation of PCL and GR in distinct non-overlapping temperature ranges and under different atmospheres. The measurements were performed on a thermogravimetric analyzer Q500 (TA Instruments, Delaware, USA). The analysis was conducted in the temperature range of 25–800 °C. The thermodegradation of PCL was carried out in an inert nitrogen atmosphere within the temperature range of 25–630 °C, after which the nitrogen was replaced by reactive synthetic oxygen in the range of 630–800 °C to burn off the graphene and the carbonaceous residues of PCL. The flow rate of both gases used was 60 mL/min. The mass fraction of GR in the fibrous material was then determined from the mass loss curve in the corresponding temperature interval.

2.4.6. Mechanical properties

To determine Young's modulus, ultimate tensile strength, and elongation, a LabTest 2.050 universal testing machine (Labortech, Opava, Czech Republic) with mechanical grips equipped with a load cell of nominal capacity 100 N was used. The tensile test was conducted in accordance with ISO 13 934–1, utilizing test specimens with working dimensions of 50 × 100 mm, subjected to a loading speed of 100 mm/min. Young's modulus and tensile strength values were calculated using the porosity values for each set of samples, determined based on the respective density (taking into account the PCL to GR ratio), volume, and mass. For each set, five specimens were tested.

2.4.7. Solvent resistance

Considering the intended final use of the prepared nanofibrous layers as extraction materials for dynamic liquid environments, the fibers were tested for their resistance to swelling or dissolving in standard HPLC mobile phases based on organic solvents (acetonitrile

and methanol). To determine the solubility in common HPLC solvents, the nanofibrous layers with PCL:graphene ratios of 10:0, 10:1, 10:5, and 10:10 were tested. These samples were immersed in acetonitrile (ACN), methanol (MeOH) and mixtures of ACN:MeOH, ACN:H₂O, and MeOH:H₂O (1:1 wt ratios). Samples of approximately 0.10 g were placed in glass vials and submerged in 4 mL of the respective solvent. They were stirred for 24 h. After removal, the samples were dried in a desiccator for 48 h. Weight loss was subsequently calculated from the mass before and after testing. SEM morphology of the samples after exposure to the solvents was performed following the methodology described above.

2.5. SPE extraction

2.5.1. Preparation of standard solutions and samples

Each standard was dissolved in methanol at a concentration 1 mg/mL to prepare the stock solution. The mixed standard stock solution was prepared by mixing 50 μ L of each standard and diluting with water to the concentration 50 mg/L. All standard stock solutions were stored at -20°C at dark. Working solutions were prepared at the day of measurement via diluting with distilled water. For testing the extracting abilities of the materials, the concentration 10 mg/L was used.

2.5.2. Preparation of extraction pre-columns

Extraction pre-columns were manually assembled by packing an appropriate amount of nanofibrous layer into an empty column cartridge (5×4.6 mm i.d.; see [Supplementary Material – S1](#)). Cartridge was connected to the on-line SPE HPLC system using the guard pre-column holder. Initially, each pre-column was washed/activated by 100 % acetonitrile, then several on-line SPE HPLC analysis cycles were performed without sample injection. Not-retained GR and other impurities and ballasts were washed out by this procedure. Column suitability for use was verified by UV detection (decreasing signal of detector).

2.5.3. The on-line SPE HPLC

An on-line SPE-HPLC system Shimadzu Nexera X2 was used for the simultaneous pre-concentration and determination of model analytes. SPE was carried out using nanofibrous pre-columns. Methanol or acetonitrile (0–40 %) was used as organic modifier in aqueous washing mobile phase at a flow rate $1.0 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. Chromatographic separations were carried out using a Kinetex® Biphenyl 150×4.6 mm, $5 \mu\text{m}$ particle size analytical column from Phenomenex (Torrance, California, USA) at a gradient of the mobile phase consisting of water (solvent A) and methanol (solvent B) at a flow rate of $1.0 \text{ mL}/\text{min}$ at temperature of 20°C .

$10 \mu\text{L}$ of sample was injected in the extraction pre-column filled with composite nanofibrous sorbent and washing mobile phase pre-concentrated the analytes. At the same time, the analytical column was equilibrated to the initial conditions of the gradient (40 % A). After 1.0 min the valve was switched and the elution of the retained analytes started. The gradient program started after switching the valve (detailed information on the gradient elution program is provided in the [Supplementary Material – S2](#)). The detection of analytes was achieved using UV detection at 220 nm and 240 nm (for hydroxypyrene and bisphenol S). The total run time was 12.5 min.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Composite nanofibrous sorbent preparation and characterization

3.1.1. Spinning solutions properties

The dynamic viscosity, electrical conductivity, and surface tension values of the selected PCL spinning solutions with added GR are presented in [Fig. 2](#). The addition of graphene nanoparticles resulted in a gradual reduction in the dynamic viscosity of the solutions (at a constant shear rate of $500/\text{s}$), decreasing from $0.139 \pm 0.04 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ for the PCL solution without GR (labelled 10:0) to 0.106 ± 0.009 for the 10:10 solution ([Fig. 2a](#)). In contrast, the electrical conductivity of the solutions significantly increased with the addition of GR, rising from an initial value of 12.5 ± 2 – $176 \pm 14 \text{ mN}/\text{m}$. Unlike viscosity, conductivity did not increase linearly; a notable rise occurred after the addition of even a small amount of GR (10:1 solution), followed by a near-exponential increase, as shown in [Fig. 2b](#).

Fig. 2. Spinning solutions properties dependence on PCL:GR ratios – dynamic viscosity at shear rate of $500/\text{s}$ (a), electrical conductivity (b) and surface tension (c).

This can be attributed to graphene's inherent high electrical conductivity, though possible impurities introduced alongside the GR may also have had an effect. The surface tension of the solutions exhibited only minor variations with the addition of GR, fluctuating around 32 mN/m (see Fig. 2c). Therefore, the primary factors influencing the subsequent electrospinning of the PCL solutions were the increase in electrical conductivity and, to a lesser degree, the reduction in viscosity. Surface tension had a minimal effect.

3.1.2. Fibrous material

The process of producing fiber layers containing GR using AC electrospinning consistently resulted in the formation of a nanofiber plume with a typical tubular shape determined by the geometry of the working electrode. The diameter of this plume increased as the GR content in the solution rose. This was likely due to the increasing electrical conductivity of the solutions, which caused greater repulsion between the identically charged material during each half-wave of the applied voltage. A visually observable decrease in the volume of transferred material was also noted with the increasing GR content, as the rising proportion of GR progressively impaired the quality of the electrospinning process. The fiber plume became less homogeneous as its diameter increased, and at higher GR concentrations, it also lost coherence, making it more difficult to collect the resulting fibrous material on the rotating collector. Fig. 3 shows the nanofiber layers produced with increasing GR content, spun using AC electrospinning. All GR concentrations in the solutions were successfully converted into nanofiber layers without visible macroscopic defects using this method. As can be seen, the layers darkened with increasing GR content, indicating a higher actual GR concentration within the layers themselves.

The observed decrease in the homogeneity of the fiber plume with increasing GR content in the electrospun solutions also affected the productivity of AC electrospinning (see Fig. 4a). Productivity dropped from the initial value of 10.7 g/h to 1.9 g/h for the solution with the highest GR concentration. The decline in productivity between the 10:1 and 10:6 ratios was more gradual, but it then decreased sharply again after reaching PCL:GR ratio of 10:7. The 10:7 ratio was therefore considered a critical point, beyond which the spinning productivity significantly declined. This decrease was caused by the reduced cohesion of the fiber plume, leading to its breakage during collection, with portions of the spun material depositing on the collector's edges or entirely missing the collector. A similar trend was observed in the areal density of the layers produced. While the productivity of the solution with the highest GR concentration (10:10) dropped to about one-fifth of that for the GR-free solution (10:0), the areal density decreased to approximately one-twelfth (from 65 to 5.5 g/m²). This reflected the aforementioned increase in the fiber plume diameter with rising GR content, along with the reduction in the productivity of the AC electrospinning process.

SEM images of the selected fibrous layers are demonstrated in Fig. 5. The native PCL material from the initial solution without GR (10:0) provided a mixture of smooth surface nanofibers. Increasing the GR content in the polymer solutions resulted in wrinkled structure of the fibers that can be attributed mainly to GR particles content. At low GR concentrations, these manifested as surface irregularities on the originally smooth fibers, followed by irregular changes in fiber diameters. At higher GR concentration, this morphological change of the fibers, especially wrinkling, is more pronounced.

Table 1 presents the resulting average fiber diameters along with their standard deviations. The fiber diameters progressively decreased with the increasing GR content in the electrospun solutions, as did the standard deviations. The higher fiber diameters and their deviations are typical for PCL prepared by AC electrospinning and do not adversely affect the material's reproducibility (Sivan et al., 2022). In the case of the 10:5 sample, batch-to-batch reproducibility was performed, which showed that the RSD between individual batches ($n = 6$) of fiber diameters was 8 % and of graphene content was 6 %. However, the standard deviations were often so high that differences between adjacent samples could not be distinctly identified. Despite this, the overall trend of decreasing diameters was clear. This phenomenon can be explained by two interrelated factors – higher electrical conductivity of the electrospun solutions and the decreasing concentration of PCL, which acted as the binding element of GR in the final product.

The measured contact angle values of water on the resulting layers are presented in Fig. 6a. Due to the hydrophobic nature of the base material (PCL) and the additive (GR), no significant change in the contact angle was observed with increasing GR content, which remained in the range of 130–140°. A similar observation applies to the relative volumetric porosity of the samples, which remained consistently at 90–95 % regardless of the amount of GR present (see Fig. 6b). However, a significant change was observed in the specific surface area. This parameter increased approximately exponentially with the concentration of GR in the electrospun solution (see Fig. 6c). This behavior can likely be attributed to the decreasing diameters of the prepared fibers and the roughening of their surfaces due to the presence of the GR particle aggregates, and the occurrence of numerous globular GR structures.

Fig. 7 presents the TGA curves of the individual fiber materials used to determine the actual GR content. The determination was based on the use of distinct and clearly separated zones of thermal decomposition, representing the mass fractions of PCL and GR, taking advantage of their different thermal degradation behaviours. The decomposition occurred at distinct temperature ranges (PCL between 240 and 440 °C and GR between 630 and 720 °C), and the analysis was conducted under different atmospheric conditions

Fig. 3. The macroscopic appearance of the resulting fiber layers with increasing PCL:GR ratios (in the corresponding spun solution).

Fig. 4. The productivity of AC electrospinning depending on the PCL:GR ratio in the solution (a), and the surface density of the resulting layers after one hour of electrospinning (b).

Fig. 5. SEM images of the electrospun material from solutions 10:0, 10:1, 10:5 and 10:10. The scales shown on the images to the left apply to all other images in the corresponding series.

Table 1

Fiber diameters (d) and the corresponding standard deviation (σ_d) as a function of the electrospun solution.

sample	10:0	10:1	10:2	10:3	10:4	10:5	10:6	10:7	10:8	10:9	10:10
d [nm]	1170	1160	960	1070	850	850	800	860	670	650	530
σ_d [nm]	570	410	280	390	210	270	250	290	200	180	230

(inert nitrogen for PCL interval and reactive synthetic oxygen for GR interval). The mass losses observed with increasing temperature correspond to the percentage weight fractions of each component, along with the incombustible residue representing impurities from both components.

The results of the TGA analyses of fiber layers are summarized in Fig. 8 and Table 2, which shows that the actual concentrations of GR in the final product were always slightly lower than the values corresponding to the composition of the respective spinning solutions. The gap between the two curves enhanced with higher concentrations of GR in the solution and was approximately 10 % of the theoretical value. Thus, the transfer efficiency of GR from the polymer solution was around 90 %, demonstrating that the designed spinning system was suitable for the effective preparation of polymer fiber layers with an ultra-high GR content.

Fig. 6. Contact angles (a), relative porosity (b), and specific surface area (c) of selected fiber layers.

Fig. 7. The TGA curves of selected fiber samples: The first significant weight loss corresponded to the thermal degradation of PCL, the second to the GR. The TGA curves of all prepared fiber samples are shown in [Supplementary material – S3](#).

The results of the TGA analysis were further supported by complementary attenuated total reflectance Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR–FTIR) using a germanium crystal, which clearly revealed the characteristic C–O–H bond peak of PCL at 1246 cm⁻¹ ([Supplementary Material – S4](#)). The presence of graphene, i.e., a specific carbon form, was reflected by an overall increase in the slope of the spectral curve compared to the control sample (10:0). The ratio of the distances between plateau regions at 930 cm⁻¹ strongly correlated with the actual graphene concentration determined by TGA, suggesting that, after further calibration, this method could serve as a rapid and cost-effective qualitative assessment of graphene content in the fibers.

Finally, a four-point probe method was used to measure electrical conductivity. Conductivity was confirmed, particularly in the 10:10 sample, where it increased with compression of the layer without loss of fibrous structure, reaching a value of 8.33 kΩ. This suggests the material's potential applicability in electrochemical systems or as a sensing element, benefiting from its flexibility and non-brittle nature ([Supplementary Material – S5](#)).

Fig. 8. The curves of mass concentrations of GR in the dry matter of the prepared fiber layers – the theoretical value corresponding to the composition of the spinning solution ($W_{theoretical}$) and the value determined by TGA analysis (W_{real}).

Table 2

Graphene wt. content of prepared PCL:GR fiber materials determined by TGA analysis.

sample	10:0	10:1	10:2	10:3	10:4	10:5	10:6	10:7	10:8	10:9	10:10
GR [%]	0.0	7.7	15.1	20.2	26.0	30.7	31.5	38.9	39.2	43.6	45.5
σ [%]	-	0.8	0.7	1.9	1.0	1.9	1.6	0.6	0.2	0.6	0.7

Fig. 9. Results of the tensile strength tests for selected fibrous materials (a) and the corresponding values of Young's modulus and maximum elongation (b).

3.1.3. Mechanical properties

For mechanical testing, four samples of prepared fibrous materials were selected – 10:0, 10:1, 10:5, and 10:10 (Fig. 9a). The tensile tests showed that with increasing GR concentration, there was a decrease in Young's modulus and maximum elongation (Fig. 9b). An exception was observed for sample 10:1, which showed higher maximum elongation. However, this difference was not statistically significant, indicating comparable elongation of samples 10:0 and 10:1. The Young's modulus for the 10:0 layer was approximately 51.4 MPa, decreasing to 5.0 MPa for the 10:10 sample. Maximum elongation values decreased from about 90 % to just under 40 %. The reduction in the mechanical properties of the individual fibrous layers was necessarily due to the decreasing concentration of PCL in the layers (as shown in the TGA analysis), which served as the fibrous binding material for GR particle clusters. Besides the reduced PCL content, the observed fiber wrinkling may also weaken the mechanical properties. Wrinkled fibers transfer stress less efficiently, their curvature can act as stress concentrators, and the reduced homogeneity of the mat further contributes to the lower values of tensile strength and Young's modulus. However, even for samples with a high GR content, the layers retained their fibrous character and did not become brittle, which is a common drawback of polymer materials highly doped with graphene particles.

In the case of raw PCL fiber sample 10:0, our previous studies have already confirmed very good SPE cartridge packing, long-term structural stability, and long-term use under high pressure (Háková et al., 2020, 2018b). Graphene-containing materials, despite decreasing mechanical properties, enabled good and repeatable filling of cartridges without long-term fluctuations in working pressure.

3.1.4. Solvent resistance

In Table 3, the percentage weight losses of fibrous layers were recorded, testing their stability in various types of solvents. The lowest long-term stability was observed in materials exposed to ACN and an ACN:MeOH mixture in a 1:1 ratio. The significant weight losses in these solvents indicated that the usability of the prepared materials in such solvents was limited. For this reason, the solvents containing a mixture of acetonitrile with water, where the weight loss of samples was below the level of experimental error, were selected for subsequent testing of the extraction properties of the fibrous materials. The 20°C as oven temperature in LC column was used while working with composite materials based on PCL, to support stability (Háková et al., 2018b).

3.2. Application of high rich graphene material for extraction

3.2.1. The effect of organic modifier on adsorption of model analytes

Firstly, the effect of organic modifier in the washing mobile phase, i.e. methanol and acetonitrile in mixture with water was tested for native PCL sorbent. The pre-column was fully packed with each material separately and connected directly to the on-line SPE-HPLC system. Duration of the washing step was set to 1 min, at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. The effect of washing mobile phase on each analyte retention is depicted in the supplementary material (S6 and S7) as a % of the retained amount in comparison to peak area of analytes in absence of the extraction step.

Methanol as an organic modifier was tested in the range 0–40 % (v/v) in water. With increasing portion of methanol in the washing mobile phase, decrease in retention of some more polar analytes (hydroxypyrene, 3-chlorophenol, bisphenol S) was observed due to faster elution (Fig. 10 a-c). Retention of bisphenol A, AF, C, Z, AP were affected by the methanol minimally. Increasing retention for kadethrin with increasing ratio of methanol on the graphene-loaded polycaprolactone is related to its better solubility in organic phase.

Acetonitrile provided different effect on the graphene-loaded materials than on native PCL. In the case of PCL, retention of analytes decreased with the increasing levels of acetonitrile. On the contrary, retention of analytes was higher in 10 % of acetonitrile than in 0 % organic modifier (except hydroxypyrene and 3-chlorophenol). Retention of kadethrin and bisphenol A on 10:10 graphene was three times higher when acetonitrile is about 20–30 % and 15 %, respectively, compared to water (see Fig. 11). Again, this effect is related to better solubility of analytes after addition of acetonitrile and their better contact with the nonpolar polymer and GR particles that can be limited in polar water compartment.

Acetonitrile probably changes interactions between analytes and graphene-loaded sorbents due to decreasing the polarity of carrier solvent. Model analytes are retained on graphene-loaded sorbents differently than in case of methanol or aqueous washing phase. Bisphenol S showed increased retention in 10 % ACN (see Fig. 12a) than in water or 20 % MeOH (Supplementary material – S8).

3.2.2. The effect of graphene on retention of model analytes

As was mentioned, enhanced retention of model analytes on graphene-loaded sorbents was significant in the case of acetonitrile in the washing mobile phase. This trend was the most significant in lower contents of graphene in fibers (Fig. 12a or chromatograms in

Table 3

Relative weight loss (wt. %) of fiber layers with theoretical PCL:GR ratios after stability testing.

solvent	10:0	10:1	10:5	10:10
CAN	35.8	15.3	20.7	10.2
ACN:MeOH (1:1)	10.4	4.6	18.1	21.2
ACN:H ₂ O (1:1)	1.5	6.5	8.2	1.3
MeOH	0.7	0.6	2.5	1.9
MeOH:H ₂ O (1:1)	0.4	0.5	2.1	4.7

Fig. 10. Effect of methanol in washing mobile phase on analyte-retention on native PCL sorbent.

Fig. 11. Effect of acetonitrile in washing mobile phase on analyte-retention on native PCL sorbent.

Fig. 12. Relative change of recovery (washing mobile phase: 10% ACN). Areas of analytes, when graphene-free PCL (sample 10:0) was used, were considered 100% and were marked by * (a) and comparison of on-line SPE HPLC chromatograms when 10:2 PCL:graphene (red line) or graphene-free PCL (dash line) was used as sorbents (washing mobile phase: 10% acetonitrile) (b).

Fig. 12b). Graphene in fibers negatively affects the retention of hydroxyppyrene and 3-chlorophenol (Fig. 12a). The best extraction of those two analytes was achieved on graphene-free PCL. Extraction properties of high rich graphene-loaded material (10:10) stand outside the graphene-loaded sorbents line. Retention of analytes on this material was enhanced only when the acetonitrile was in the washing mobile phase (minimal content 10% of acetonitrile in water). This phenomenon could be explained by worse wettability of GR rich material in water compartment and thus poor contact of analytes with sorbent in high pressure flow system. Retention of deltamethrin was increased on the graphene loaded material (from 10:1–10:5) when stronger washing mobile phase (20% methanol or 10% acetonitrile) was used. It fits well with the deltamethrin solubility and better wettability of the highly nonpolar sorbent after addition of organic part to mobile phase.

4. Conclusion

This study describes the new approach of fabrication composite nanofibrous material consisting of poly- ϵ -caprolactone and high graphene content (up to 45 wt%) using the alternating current electrospinning method from a polymer solution. The properties of eleven solutions in a concentration series with varying PCL:GR ratios were investigated, focusing on their spinnability, as well as the surface morphology and mechanical properties of the resulting materials. As the GR concentration in the spinning solutions increased, a gradual decrease in the productivity of the electrospinning process was observed, with a significant drop occurring beyond the spinning of fibers containing more than approximately 35 wt% of GR. These materials still exhibited good mechanical properties without becoming brittle, and thus suitable for coupling to high pressure chromatography system. Finally, all materials were tested for

extraction purposes for phenolic water pollutants in cartridge coupled on-line to HPLC system.

Graphene-loaded materials showed good mechanical stability for on-line SPE-HPLC application. Strong effect of organic modifier in washing mobile phase was observed. Retention of model analytes on graphene-loaded material increased in washing mobile phase with addition of organic solution (20 % MeOH or 10 % ACN). On the contrary when the graphene-free PCL sorbent was used, addition of the organic solvent to washing mobile phase caused the loss of analytes and negatively affected the peak shape during chromatography separation (increasing tailing). Graphene-loaded materials showed higher extraction yield for model analytes (except of 3-chlorophenol and hydroxypyrene) than graphene free PCL when 10 % ACN was used in the washing mobile phase. Stronger washing mobile phase (with addition of small portion of organic modifier) is desirable in the sample extraction step in high-pressure flow system for better wettability of GR rich sorbents. The increased retention was significant for materials covering the range from approximately 7–30 wt% of graphene in the fibers. Given the aforementioned properties, the prepared materials can be successfully utilized as an advanced alternative to commercial SPE sorbents for environmental water analysis, especially phenolic pollutants.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Dalibor Šatínský: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Martina Háková:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Ivona Količová:** Visualization, Data curation. **Jakub Erben:** Validation, Resources, Investigation. **Pavel Holec:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Jan Vinter:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Tomáš Kalous:** Investigation, Data curation. **Markéta Klíčová:** Investigation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that this manuscript is original, has not been published before and is not currently being considered for publication elsewhere. Furthermore, the authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.eti.2025.104591](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eti.2025.104591).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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